

Ufra-infected plants in Orissa, India, 1987.

in size, often partially emerged, deformed, and chaffy (see figure).

Large numbers of males and juveniles but only a few females of the nematode were recovered from the axils of affected boot leaves.

Symptoms of ufra had been found before in Cuttack and Balasore, but the nematode could not be recovered. The current identification confirms presence of the nematode in a new locality and in a new habitat. □

Population dynamics of rice root nematode *Hirschmanniella oryzae* in rice of different durations

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We measured the population density of *H. oryzae* from 500-cm³ soil samples taken monthly in Jul-Dec 1987 from field plots where RD25, RD27, and LPT123 were grown as short-, medium-, and long-duration varieties. RD27 and LPT123 were seeded in Jul, RD25 in Aug. RD25 was harvested in Nov, RD27 in Dec, and LPT123 in Jan.

Nematodes (no./500 cm³ soil)

Density of rice root nematode *H. oryzae* in rice varieties of different durations at Pathum Thani Rice Research Center, Thailand, 1987 wet season.

Nematode population in RD25 had only one peak—in Nov (see figure). Both RD27 and LPT123 had two

peaks—Aug and Nov. Highest population density in all varieties occurred in Nov. □

Host range and feeding preference of golden apple snail

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Golden apple snail *Pomacea canaliculata* has become an important

pest of rice in the Philippines. During the pre-planting period, golden apple snails are usually found in irrigation canals and drainage ditches, where they may be feeding on weeds.

We tested eight common species of lowland weeds and rice to determine the host range and feeding preference of golden apple snail.

Table 1. Golden apple snail host preference. IRRI, 1987.

Plant species	Plants (5%) consumed by the snails ^a at indicated time (h after infestation)			
	4 h	24 h	48 h	72 h
<i>Monochoria vaginalis</i>	50 a	100 a	100 a	100 a
<i>Echinochloa glabrescens</i>	40 a	100 a	100 a	100 a
<i>Cyperus difformis</i>	35 a	90 a	100 a	100 a
<i>Oryza sativa</i>	0 b	100 a	100 a	100 a
<i>Fimbristylis miliacea</i>	0 b	100 a	100 a	100 a
<i>Paspalum distichum</i>	20 ab	55 b	85 ab	90 a
<i>Ipomoea aquatica</i>	0 b	20 c	75 b	85 a
<i>Sphenoclea zeylanica</i>	0 b	48 b	52 c	52 b
<i>Pistia stratiotes</i>	0 b	30 bc	45 c	48 b

^aAv of 10 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.